

The Visionary Leadership's impact on the Strategic role of proactive Orientation: an Analytical Research in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade

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Abstract: The tagged research (the impact of visionary leadership on the strategic role of proactive orientation), dealt with the recognition of the extent of the impact of visionary leadership in its dimensions (communication, vision, and empowerment) in the proactive orientation with its strategic framework represented by dimensions (exploring the future, searching for new opportunities, experience and experimentation), it also sought to achieve a set of goals, the most important of which is identifying and diagnosing the nature of the correlative, consensual and influential relationship, with both research's variables, starting from a problem centered in the weakness or absence of the visionary side of working leaders in the productive sector, which weakened the organizational role for expecting the external environment and exploring guarantee opportunities to meet the market need and the requirements of society, which is considered as a clear challenge in front of such sectors.

The research used the descriptive analytical method, besides the questionnaire as a measurement tool in collecting information that was distributed by (42) questionnaires on an intentional and intended sample, which was represented workers from the categories (senior management's managers, departments' managers, units and sections) in the General Company for Grain Trade by using quintile, the five-step Likert scale. The sample was subjected to tests of apparent fidelity and consistency, by using a number of statistical means, the most important of which are the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and simple and multiple linear regressions, in addition to the use of the computer program (SPSS.V.22). Through their work on this research, the researchers were able to prove the validity of the main hypothesis, according to which (visionary leadership has statistical significant effect on the proactive orientation). The research also came out with a set of recommendations that serve the purpose of the research for which it was prepared, the most important of which is the need to work on enhancing the qualifications and skills of administrative leaders and to pay more interest in the strategic vision aspect, in order to draw a future picture with a clear and insightful vision about the organization's future to advance the company's reality and to enhance its capabilities and proactive

orientations for opportunities in the environment and to confront unexpected challenges and events, which may positively reflect on the outputs of the productive sector and its societal performance.

Key words: visionary leadership, prospective orientation, strategic orientations

Introduction

If we look at today theoretical business organizations, we will find that they have changed clearly and substantially from what they were. The unstable environment and the changes and challenges which were sorted by the circumstances of the accelerating environmental factors, have become more influential, and forced them to confront and review their decisions continuously by adopting strategies for the survival and continuity. Thus, it became necessary to adapt to this environment, and from here there must be a leadership with a long-term vision which is able to deal quickly with the dynamic changes. Hence, the research discusses the role of the visionary leadership in supporting the strategic role of proactive orientation, in an attempt to reduce the gap between two important and vital variables, and at the same time, they are considered as two necessary requirements for the survival of organizations and their continuation. On the other hand, it creates a value in the markets, and this may encroach that of global markets, as stated in (Blocker et al, 2011) study, which emphasized the importance and role of the proactive orientation in creating value for customers in global markets through the performance of a new product, and in response to create superior value. On the other hand, Zaid's study (2011) called for knowing and measuring the importance of vision for workers and its impact on the organization's effectiveness and his study was targeted the higher education institutions, and tested Kyambogo University as a case study to reach the goal. In the same direction, the Dhammik's study (2014) came to show the role of visionary leadership on the behavior of organizational citizenship, so it was founded that there was a strong positive relationship between them. Hence, the current research was prepared to be applied in a different environment and in a different orientation that addresses the impact of visionary leadership with an environmental exploratory strategic orientation, and to tackle the problem of the deficiency of managers and leaders' view of these variables in order to achieve a primary goal of the researched organization in the Iraqi productive environment.

The research was applied in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade and by adopting an intentional and intended sample, which number is (42) from the company's managers, and to reach the research's results, the questionnaire was also adopted as a measurement tool, according to the quintile Likert scale (agreed totally, agreed, neutral, disagree, disagree totally), and by using a number of statistical means to prove the validity of the main hypothesis, including the arithmetic mean, the standard deviation, and simple and multiple linear regression equation, as the researchers found that there is (a correlation relationship and influence with a statistical significant function for the visionary leadership on the proactive orientation at the macro level and at the level of sub-dimensions).

The research dealt with four searches, the first search covered the research's methodology, while the second one was devoted to outline the theoretical side with the concepts of both research's variables, whereas the third search was dealt with the practical application side of testing hypotheses. As for the fourth one, it addressed the most important conclusions that emerged from the results of the research, as it came out with a set of recommendations that serve the purpose for which it was prepared.

1. Research Methodology.

First: Research Problem

The research's problem is embodied in what the business organizations are suffering at the present time to face events as a real reaction to what their environment endures from opportunities or threats. It also needs to invest its strength in order to enhance its position and prominence in the business environment, such an environment that does not calm down at any case and with a frightening acceleration, which requires from the organization management to prospect and to precede new events when they occur. The environment of the Iraqi general Company for Grain Trade has witnessed changing circumstances with the lack of financial allocations that prevented the market from being satisfied with the product and the failure to provide the required and necessary service in order to supply the consumer with the appropriate amount for his personal consumption. This has led to an inconsistency between production decisions and market requirements, and this may be due to a lack of focus or the absence of a visionary side for the working leaders in this sector (the field). The strategic proactive orientation needs a real leadership with a strategic vision that is directed towards action and taking risks, and provided opportunities that enhance the organization's ability to meet its needs and components. However, the Iraqi organizations have suffered from the isolation of the developments and changes in their environment compared to the organizations of other countries, especially after the sole openness with the international markets. Hence, the great role of a visionary leadership appears so that it can address this dilemma. Therefore, the research problem is embodied by the main question, what is the extent of the relationship between visionary leadership and proactive orientation as an important strategic orientation in the current business environment represented by the General Company for Grain Trade, and how can visionary leadership influence a proactive exploration of the organization's environment?

Second: Research Importance

The importance of the research lies in the significance of its variables in the contemporary business environment and in clarifying the importance of the strategic vision as a significant characteristic for strategic leader that the most of our Iraqi organization lack, in addition to the importance of the role that the vision plays in achieving a proactive orientation from which one can benefit as a process of growth and survival of the organization for the longest possible period in the business environment.

Third: Research objectives

The current research aims to identify the availability of the visionary leadership characteristics for the working leaders in the researched company, and the extent of its impact on the proactive orientations with a strategic framework, in a way that opens up the organization's prospects for new ideas and a tendency towards the change through exploiting new opportunities.

Fourth: Research hypotheses

The first major hypothesis *

The visionary leadership is related to its dimensions (vision, communication, and empowerment), with a correlation that has significant and statistical indication (function) in the dimensions of proactive orientation. **The following sub-hypotheses are derived from the first main hypothesis:**

- 1.The visionary leadership is linked to its dimensions (vision, communication, and empowerment), with a significant function in exploring the future.
2. The visionary leadership is linked to its dimensions (vision, communication, and empowerment) with a correlation that has a significant indication in searching for new opportunities.
- 3.The visionary leadership is related to its dimensions (vision, communication, and empowerment); with a correlation that has a significant indication in the experiences and experimentation.

* The second main hypothesis

The visionary leadership, with its dimensions (vision, communication, and empowerment) has a statistical significant effect on proactive orientation. From the second main hypothesis, the following sub-hypotheses are derived:-

- 1.The visionary leadership, with its dimensions (vision, communication, empowerment), has an effect that has a statistical significant indication in exploring the future.
2. The visionary leadership, with its dimensions (vision, communication, and empowerment) has an effect that has statistical and significant indication in searching for new opportunities.
- 3.The visionary leadership, with its dimensions (vision, communication, and ability) has an effect that has statistical and significant indication in the experiences and experimentation.

Fifth: the form for a hypothetical search

Figure (1)the form for a hypothetical search

Source: prepared by the researchers

Sixth: Research Methodology

An analytical-descriptive approach was adopted because this approach is distinguished with an inclusive view, beside the description of the case being associated with its analysis and interpretation of what is being realistically, and then extracting the main results and indicators by using the description of collecting information and data included in the research for the purpose of reaching the results and finding its most prominent indicators.

Seventh: The measuring instrument

for obtaining data on the research variables related to the field side, the questionnaire was designed with its paragraphs based on the adopted and ready-made standards in the sober previous scientific studies, after making adjustments to it according to what is appropriate to the requirements of the current research and according to what is appropriate to the Iraqi environment in which the research was conducted. Table (1) shows the composition of the questionnaire, its main and subsidiary variables, and the sources of its paragraphs with the used measure.

Table 1: Research main and sub dimensions, number of its paragraphs, and used measure

used source	paragraphs	sub dimension	main dimension
Westly&Mintzborg,1989 al-Tememi ,2016	1-7	vision	visionary leadership
	8-14	communication	
	15-20	empowerment	
Qasim ,2011 Blocker et al,2011 Dominguez et al,2010	21-26	exploring future	proactive orientation
	27-32	search for new opportunities	
	33-37	experiences and experimentation	

The second search: conceptual theoretical framework for the research variables

First: the visionary leadership

One of the most important points of a successful leadership is to reflect its ability to perceive and anticipate the future clearly and accurately, such ability is important to face future obstacles and to develop appropriate solutions to overcome them (Rawoiiie, 2010: 3), and here the importance of visionary leadership appears as an important factor for the survival of organizations, and growth in a changing and unstable, environment. Perhaps this is the biggest and most prominent challenge that is facing the business organizations, because the visionary leadership is based on commitment to spiritual values with the ability to inspire and analyze with drawing a clear vision for a future that is full of futuristic insight into courageous and creative work (Dwivedi, 2006: 11) and according to (Marno) the visionary leader possesses always the orientation to the future (Anshar, 2017: 53).And since the effective communication is very important to a leader with a correct and positive vision that supports his subordinates, the absence of this vision makes individuals do not respond to the organization's vision and goals and do not seek to achieve their common goals (Nwachukwu et al, 2017: 1303).

Bunnoiko & Atthirawong, 2017: 398) defined it as "one's ability to perceive the future and clearly anticipate it so that it can prepare to face unexpected consequences."

However (Kusmiyati & Efendy, 2017: 70) was found it as "the ability to create or formulate ideal ideas and social communication, and to transform those ideas into a result of social interaction between members of the organization and stakeholders."

Therefore, the visionary leadership reflects the leader's ability to draw a vision with possibilities to implement it, as it is an ongoing dynamic and interactive phenomenon in achieving the goals of the principals, stakeholders and the organization.

And (Mupa) adds that it represents a pillar and a basic basis for achieving innovation and bringing the organization to the highest levels of performance improvement, by describing the ideal situation for the principals and identifying the gap between the current situation and the ideal state of the organization and working to reduce it (Mupa, 2015: 43-44).

Accordingly, the two researchers see the visionary leadership as the ability to create a vision with a strategic framework and communicate it to the subordinates, which is expressing a view of a desirable future situation through looking forward to the future, with an ability to persuade others to commit to it and achieve it, after it is taking over their hearts and pushing them towards implementation, and thus determines the role of the leader in (communicating, stimulating and implementing) a strategic vision or in making the change.

Second: Visionary leadership characteristics

According to (Mora-Whitehurst, 2013: 318), the visionary leadership has three characteristics:-

1. Idealism: It assumes the leader's positive influence on the organization as personal behavior and characteristics that he can demonstrate as a basic behavior of leadership.

2. Confidence: it is related to the visionary leader who has a positive influence with self-confidence, and that confidence is the basis of the behaviors of the leader who seeks to bring about change and impact on others.

3. Authorization: It reflects the leader's need for power to grant rewards and control over others who realize that the strength and influence are enough to accomplish important things in organizations, by strengthening authority, teamwork, empowerment and professionalism. **Nurut adds (2016: 37-38) the following two characteristics:-**

1. The audacity to take steps and decisions to change the old form and create unconventional and unfamiliar strategies.

2. Commitment to spiritual values and show energy, vitality and desire.

As for the roles of visionary leadership, (Nindyati, 2013: 4-5) has identified four roles that are summarized in each of (direction finder, coach, speaker and change agent).

The two researchers believe that there are correlative relationships between the characteristics of the visionary leadership and the roles, as it requires a specific directional role, a characteristic of confidence and idealism, whereas the trainer and the speaker are clearly related to the attribute of authorization

The Visionary Leadership's impact on the Strategic role of proactive orientation An analytical research in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade

and audacity, while the change factor is closely related to the commitment feature. Therefore, it can be said that the visionary leadership behavior will create trends and the ability to express and define new strategies and scenarios for their organizations that define these trends.

Many researchers unanimously agreed on several dimensions of the visionary leadership, but the majority of them agreed only on three basic dimensions (Westly & Mintzberg, 1989), (Fendi and others, 2013) and (Daft, 2001), which are:-

1. **The vision:** It expresses a fictional image and an idea about the future of the organization, in addition to enhance the positive perceptions of both the leader and the subordinates (Kwan, 2013: 21). It also plays a vital role in creating and adopting the values and the distinctive identity of the organization, by uniting the members of the organization, and attributing their sense of belonging.

2. **The communication:** It refers to the qualitative transition of the organization in the future by managers, so it relates to the vision and mobilization of teamwork among members (Venus, 2013: 13). The use of effective communication by vision's leaders to change attitudes leads to organizational transformations, so it is very important for the visionary leader to obtain the support of the co-leaders, (Nwachukwu et al.2017:1303).

3. **The empowerment:** It is one of the essentials of the visionary leader, as it contributes to provide the optimum level of clarifying goals. It conveys common goals to it and sends a sense of ownership that stimulates looking towards the goal, as well as providing some kind of excitement for cooperation between the leader and subordinates (Kearney et al, 2019: 5). Thus, it represents the conscious efforts to innovate by enabling the workers and then leads to a change in the state of harmony for the society groups (Erđiaw-Kwasie & Acheampong, 2018: 934).

It is clear from this that visionary leaders possess behaviors that enable them to change the orientations of their organizations or respond to their environment, it means that they have the skills and ability to diagnose the need for the creativity and excellence and to expect what the future will be like.

Second: The strategic role of proactive orientation

In light of the acceleration of the change and the environmental activity surrounding the organization, and the proactive strategic movement that is not fixed and unstable in the market, and everything that would be reflected in the creation of expertise, as it is a key of achieving the advantage - that is, to find a positive relationship between the gained experience and the cost of produced unit (Johnson & Scholesm, 2002: 347), it was necessary to find ways to anticipate the requirements of the environment and to shape its trends to seize opportunities or a grabbing act of opportunities, it was called the strategic proactive orientation (Dess & Lumpking, 1996: 147).

It was defined as the effective behavior of the organization and the adopted initiative by the organization for creativity, innovation and renewal (Di Benedetto & Song, 2003: 77), so the proactivity relates to market opportunities (the environment) before the new entry process, and the mechanism that reflects that entry.

From a strategic organizational perspective, Aragon-Corred (1998: 55) looked at the proactivity as "the degree to which an organization directs towards initiations to make change in its strategic methods rather than a real reaction to market's demands, so the organizations." according to the researcher (Miles & Snow, 1978), it differs in its proactive orientation from other organizations, and this difference comes within three aspects or dimensions:-

The first dimension is the pioneer dimension, in which the organization is distinguished from others by analyzing the content of each phenomenon to achieve growth by changing the mode of work or developing a product or creating a new market.

The engineering dimension, in which the organization invests heavily in order to enhance its position and its technological precedence, as it possesses technological flexibility to meet any challenge or respond to any development in its environment.

The administrative dimension, through which the organization tends towards building organizational structures that reduce the degree of uncertainty and resolve the complexity, with decentralization in which it allows its employees to participate in business while imposing control on its external environment in order to respond quickly to any signs of opportunity or threat.

Therefore, the proactive organizations that have (pioneering, engineering, administrative) trends are called prospective organizations (prospectors), to distinguish them from non-proactive organizations, that is, non-prospective organizations(defenders) whereas the organizations that fall between these two terms, they have been called analyzing organization(analyzers).

The proactivity reflects an aspect of the organization's strategic position, its ability and capacity to anticipate new developments in its time (Frank, et al, 2010: 176).

This may go beyond those proactive organizations that seek to create value for the organization towards its clients by providing continuous solutions to them, and identifying their future requirements throughout generating and exchanging intelligence information about these requirements and taking measures to meet those needs (Blocker, et l, 2011: 217). This may exceed the organizational behavior related to the generation and dissemination of market information, represented by knowing the customers and their needs through the research and development processes that distinguish the organization from other competitors in the same sector (Hamzah, et al, 2015: 112). The most important elements of the proactive orientation are focused on (Al-Dulaimi, 2016: 57) -

1.Exploring the future: It may give another meaning to prospect the future, and this debate is due to the true meaning of the intended concept of prospection that is to confront the future or the reaction to threats that business organizations may face, where the organization here within this meaning can use forward-prospection to prepare for the future and to draw the scenarios (Cahier du LIPSOR, 2005: 12).

2.Searching for new opportunities: The search for new opportunities represents the organization's ability to go and open towards its environment to search for those opportunities, and that requires new knowledge that differs from existing knowledge. the most important features of it, are the differences, the flexibility, and ability to search and investigate (Rene, et al, 2005), and this requires the organization to manage a broad technological base, with the ability to respond to the opportunity and to exploit it quickly and continuously (Miles & Snow, 2012: 19).

The Visionary Leadership's impact on the Strategic role of proactive orientation An analytical research in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade

3. Experiences and experimentation: Experience and experimentation may bring talent and insight in achieving a balance between the interests of the various parties, with ability for environmental analysis, where the external environment provides the opportunities from which risks are resulted, thus they are investing in identifying a proactive orientation to market leadership.

(Johnson et al.) said if the organization wants to maintain its superiority in the market, it should do proactive moves in front of its competitors in order to be the first and foremost move to achieve the benefits of economies of scale, investment with the experience curve and cost reduction (Johnson, et al, 2008: 100).

It is clear from this that the proactive orientation is the active behavior of the organization towards preempting opportunities, as it reflects part of its strategic position in its ability to foresee the events and developments in order to be as a motivation for it in front of its other competitors, and to strengthen the competitive position.

The third search: Research analytical framework

In this search, the data obtained from the designed questionnaire will be presented and analyzed in the light of a five-graded Likert scale, which is distributed from its highest weight, where it is given a score (5) to represent the answer field (totally agree), and to its lowest weight is given a score (1) to represent the answer field (totally disagree), with the aim of presenting and analyzing the responses of the sample's individuals and their perceptions on the research variables and their sub-dimensions and the test of the study's hypotheses.

First: testing the validity of the scale

The stability test was carried out by using the half-way point method (Spearman Brown and Gittmann) with the aim of knowing the stability value of the scale, which means the stability of the obtained results (the difference in the conditions of applying the test), also, the honesty was tested in a way (self-honesty) with the aim of knowing the truth of the scale, which means whether the scale measures what was set to measure it (the extent of the test's representation for the behavior to be represented).

Table 2: shows the values of the validity and stability coefficients for the scale

Self-honesty (square root of stability)		Stability(half-way point)	
Gittmann	Spearman Brown	Gittmann	Spearman Brown
0.88	0.89	0.784	0.788

Source: Prepared by the two researchers using the output of the (spss) program

It is clear from the values of the above stability and honesty and for the two used methods that they are greater than (0.67), and therefore the scale is characterized by high stability and honesty and is suitable for the application and it useful for its outputs.

Second: Testing the normal distribution

The conduct of statistical analysis of the data requires the availability of certain conditions, the most important of which is the distribution of data naturally. A (Kulmkov_Smernov) test was conducted for the research's variables and their sub-dimensions, and it was found that all of them are subject to the normal distribution and as follows:-

Table (3) shows the values of Kulmkov-Smirnov (K_S)

Proactive orientation	Visionary leadership	Experiences and experimentation	Search for opportunities	Exploring the future	empowerment	communication	vision	variable / dimension
0.086*	0.119**	0.141*	0.131**	0.129**	0.106**	0.10**	0.112**	قيمة K_S(

The sign (*) indicates that the value of (K_S) is significant, assuming a moral significant level (0.05), meaning that (P_value) is greater than (0.05)

The sign (**) indicates that the value of (K_S) is (significant)assuming a moral (significant) level of (0.01), meaning that (P.value) is greater than (0.01).

Source: Prepared by the two researchers who depended on the outputs of SPSS program.

The Visionary Leadership's impact on the Strategic role of proactive orientation An analytical research in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade

Third: the respondents' perceptions about the research's variables and their sub-dimensions

For this purpose, the researchers used the weighted arithmetic mean, the standard deviations, and the relative importance, in order to identify the extent of harmony and consistency in the sample opinions and their perceptions about the research's variables, then the test criterion was used, represented by the hypothetical mean of (3) as the mean of the measuring instrument in order to measure and evaluate the obtained score related to the responses of the study sample individuals and as follows:-

1. Sample individuals' perceptions on the independent variable (: x visionary leadership) and its dimensions: -

Table 4: shows the responses of the sample's individuals and their perceptions of (visionary leadership) and its dimensions

arranged by importance	Arithmetic mean test compared to hypothetical mean	relative importance	standard deviation	arithmetic mean	dimensions
first	Greater than the hypothetical mean	66%	0.28	3.28	X ₁ : vision
second	Greater than the hypothetical mean	62%	0.40	3.1	X ₂ : communication

third	Greater than the hypothetical mean	61%	0.46	3.06	X ₃ : empowerment
	Greater than the hypothetical mean	63%	0.38	3.15	X: visionary leadership

Source: Prepared by the two researchers using the output of the spss program

It appears through the above table that the percentage of agreement among the individuals of the research's sample is close to the three dimensions of visionary leadership, and they are arranged according to importance (vision, communication, empowerment) respectively, where the relative importance of each of them is greater than (60%), the means for each of them was greater than the hypothetical mean which is (3). The values of the arithmetic mean for the visionary leadership's variable and its dimensions indicate a neutral direction when classified on the Likert scale, and their answers are largely homogeneous on these dimensions. This is evident from the very small standard deviation value, which indicates a weak dispersion of the answer.

- Sample individuals' perceptions on the dependent variable (Y: proactive orientation) and its dimensions:-

Table 5: shows the responses of the sample's individuals and their perceptions on (proactive orientation) and its dimensions

arranged by importance	Arithmetic mean test compared to hypothetical mean	relative importance	standard deviation	arithmetic mean	dimensions
first	Greater than the hypothetical mean	65%	0.37	3.25	Y ₁ : exploring the future
second	Greater than the hypothetical mean	65%	0.33	3.23	Y ₂ : search for new opportunities
third	Greater than the hypothetical mean	59%	0.42	2.95	Y ₃ : experiences and experimentation
	Greater than the hypothetical mean	63%	0.37	3.14	Y: proactive orientation

Source: Prepared by the two researchers using the output of the spss program

It is clear from the above table that the percentage of agreement among the members of the research sample is close to the three dimensions of proactive orientation, and they are arranged according to importance (exploring the future , searching for new opportunities, experiences and experimentation) respectively, where the relative importance of two dimensions (exploring the future, searching for new opportunities) was equal to (65%), while the relative importance of the dimension (experiences and experimentation) was equal to (59%), and the arithmetic mean for the two (exploring the future, searching for new opportunities) was greater than the hypothetical mean of (3), whereas the dimension of (experiences and experimentation) did not pass the hypothesis test and it was less than (3). The values of the arithmetic mean of the visionary leadership's variable and its dimensions indicates a

The Visionary Leadership's impact on the Strategic role of proactive orientation An analytical research in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade

neutral direction when classified on the Likert scale and indicates a modest level of visionary leadership and indicators that are available in the researched company, even if it is above the hypothetical mean, and that their response is largely homogeneous on these dimensions and that is evident from the value of the very small standard deviation, this indicates a weak dispersion in the sample's answer.

Fourth: Measuring, testing and analyzing the relationship of correlation and impact between study variables

For testing the main and secondary research hypotheses, the two researchers used inferential statistics methods (normal distribution test, linear correlation Pearson coefficient, simple linear regression, multiple linear regressions) and as follows:-

1. Testing the first main hypothesis (correlation hypothesis):

For testing the first main hypothesis and the hypotheses that derive from it, the matrix of correlation between visionary leadership and proactive orientation and their dimensions has been calculated as in the below:-

Table (6) Matrix of correlation coefficients (Pearson) between visionary leadership and proactive orientation and their sub-dimensions

Y: proactive orientation	Y ₃ : experiences and experimentation	Y ₂ : search for new opportunities	Y ₁ : exploring the future	X y
0.344*	0.430**	.002	0.308*	X ₁ : vision
0.502**	0.361*	0.673**	0.155	X ₂ : communication
0.254	0.123	0.535**	-.029	X ₃ : empowerment
0.448**	0.347*	0.560**	0.145	X: visionary leadership
<p>The sign (*) indicates that the correlation is moral (significant) (statistical indicator) assuming a significant level (0.05), meaning that (P_value) is less than (0.05).</p> <p>The sign (**) indicates that the correlation is moral (significant) (statistical indication assuming a moral (significant) level (0.01), meaning that (P_value) is less than (0.01).</p> <p>The absence of one of the two signs which are mentioned above, indicates that the correlation is not significant statistical indicatio, this means that the correlation is absent.</p>				

Source: Prepared by the two researchers using the output of the spss program

The above correlation matrix shows the following: -

- There is a moderate positive significant relationship of correlation (statistical indication) under a significant level (0.05) between the vision and the exploration of the future, which value is equal to (0.308), while it was found that there is no correlation between the exploration of the future with each of (communications, empowerment), and that the correlation coefficient between the variable of visionary leadership in general and the exploration of the future is not significant, which means rejecting the first sub hypothesis from the first main hypothesis, which states that (the vision leadership is related to its dimensions (vision, communication, empowerment) with a correlation that has a statistical moral indication in exploring the future.

- There is not a statistical indication correlation between the vision's dimension and search for new opportunities, whereas, there is the correlation between each of (communication, empowerment) and the search for new opportunities was medium and positive, besides it is a moral indication below a moral level (0.01), where its values reaches respectively (0.673) and (0.535), while the correlation coefficient between the visionary leadership in general and the dimension of searching for new opportunities is (0.560), which is a positive, medium correlation coefficient below the moral level (0.01), which shows the acceptance of the second sub-hypothesis from the first main hypothesis which states that (the visionary leadership is related to its dimensions (vision, communication, empowerment) with a correlation having a statistical moral indication in searching for new opportunities).
- There is a medium positive correlation relationship as a statistical indication between each of (the vision and communications) and the dimension of the experiences and experimentation, its values reaches respectively (0.430), (0.361), it is also evident that there is no moral correlation relationship between the dimension of the empowerment, experiences and experimentation, while the correlation between the variable of visionary leadership in general and the dimension of experiences and experimentation was moral, positive, and statistical function, where its value reached (0.347), which indicates the acceptance of the third sub-hypothesis from the first main hypothesis, and it states that (visionary leadership is related to its dimensions (vision, communication, empowerment) with a correlation having statistical moral indication in the experiences and experimentation).
- The value of the total correlation coefficient between the independent variable (visionary leadership) and the dependent variable (proactive orientation) was (0.448), and it is a medium, positive value, where it is as a statistical indication below the moral level (0.01), which means the acceptance of the first major hypothesis ,which states that (the visionary leadership is related to its dimensions (vision, communications, empowerment) with correlation having a statistical moral indication in the dimensions of the proactive orientation, and a matrix of the spread's line and below figure shows the correlations between variables and dimensions:

2. Testing the second main hypothesis (impact hypothesis):

For testing the second main hypothesis and its sub- hypotheses, the table of variance analysis was calculated for the simple linear regression between the independent variable (visionary leadership) and its dimensions and the dependent variable (proactive orientation) and its dimensions as shown below:-

Table 7: Values (F) and determination coefficient (R²) between visionary leadership and the proactive orientation's dimensions

Y ₃ : experiences and experimentation		Y ₂ : searching for new opportunities		Y ₁ : exploring the future		X ← y
R ²	F	R ²	F	R ²	F	value (F) and (R ²)
0.19	9.747 ^{**}	0	0	0.095	4.499 [*]	X ₁ : vision
0.13	6.424 [*]	0.45	35.64 ^{**}	0.024	1.054	X ₂ : communication

The Visionary Leadership's impact on the Strategic role of proactive orientation An analytical research in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade

0.015	0.658	0.29	17.28**	0.001	0.036	X ₃ :empowerment
<p>The sign (*) refers to the highest value of (F) and that the effect is significant (statistical indication assuming significant level (0.05), meaning that (P_value) is less than (0.05). The sign (**) refers to the highest value of (F) and that the effect is significant (statistical indication assuming a (significant) level (0.01), meaning that (P_value) is less than (0.01). The absence of one of the two signs above mentioned indicates that the effect is not (significant) statistical indication, it means that there is no effect.</p>						
<p>The (significance) of the regression model is tested by the value of (F), while the value of the determining factor (R2) represents the explanatory capacity (power) of the model</p>						

Source: Prepared by the two researchers using the output of the spss program

The above table shows the following: -

- The presence of a significant effect (statistical indication for the vision's dimension in exploring the future, as the calculated value of (F) reached (4,499) which is a significant indication below the significant level (0.05), and the explanatory capacity of the model was weak, but both dimensions of (communication, empowerment) have no moral effect in exploring the future, which means rejecting the first sub-hypothesis from the second main hypothesis which states that (visionary leadership affects its dimensions (vision, communication, empowerment) with an effects that has a statistical significant indication in exploring the future).

- There was no significant effect for the vision's dimension in searching for new opportunities, while there was a significant effect (statistical indication for the two dimensions (communications, empowerment) separately in the dimension of searching for new opportunities where the calculated value of (F) for each of them respectively (35.64) , (17.28), which is a significant indication below the level of (0.01), and that the explanatory capacity of each of them was good, as the value of the determination coefficient (R2) for each of them respectively (45%), (29%), which means that the communication explains about (45%) of the changes that occur in the search for new opportunities, and that empowerment explains about (29%) of the changes that occur in the search for new opportunities, and the rest is due to other variables, therefore the second sub-hypothesis of the second main hypothesis will be accepted, which states that (visionary leadership affects its dimensions (vision, communication, empowerment) with statistical moral (significant) effect in the search for new opportunities).

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The presence of a significant effect (statistical indicator) for the two dimensions (vision, communication) in the dimension of experience and experimentation where the calculated values of (F) for them reached respectively (9,747) and (6,424), which is a significant indication below the significant level (0.01) and (0.05) respectively , and the vision explains about (19%) of the changes that happen in the experiences and experimentation, and that the communication explains about (13%) of the changes that happen in the dimension of experiences and experimentation, and that the rest is due to other variables, while it was found that there was no moral effect for the empowerment's dimension in the experiences and experimentation, and thus the third sub-hypothesis of the second main hypothesis was accepted, which states that (visionary leadership affects its dimensions (vision,

communication, empowerment) with an effect that has statistical significant effect in the experiences and experimentation.

In order to know the effect of the independent variable for the visionary leadership represented by its dimensions (vision, communication, and empowerment), a multiple linear regression analysis was conducted with the aim of measuring the effect completely and as shown in the following table:-

Table 8: values (F) and determination coefficient (R2) between the dimensions of visionary leadership and proactive orientation

Multiple regression results		(Y في (X تأثير ابعاد)
Y: proactive orientation		$X_1, X_2, X_3 \leftarrow y \leftarrow$
R ²	F	
0.36	7.539**	X ₁ : vision
		X ₂ :communication
		X ₃ : empowerment

Source: Prepared by the two researchers using the output of the spss program

Through the values of (F) in the above table, it is clear that there is a significant effect (statistical indicator) of the dimensions of the visionary leadership's variable (vision, communication, empowerment) in the proactive orientation's variable, where the calculated value of (F) reached (7.539), which is a significant indication below the moral level (0.01), and the dimensions of the independent variable of the visionary leadership (vision, communication, empowerment) explain about (36%) of the changes that take place in the proactive orientation, and the rest is due to other variables, including a random error, which leads us to accept the main second hypothesis stated that (visionary leadership affects its dimensions (vision, communication, empowerment) with an effect that has statistical significant effect in the proactive orientation.

Figure (2) the impact's relationships between the visionary leadership with its dimensions and the proactive orientation

The fourth search: conclusions and recommendations

First: The conclusions:

1. It is evident that the company has a clear vision according to the requirements of the organization with the ability to predict the results of each alternative and the ability to interpret and change that vision.
2. There is an interest from company leadership to train its employees, and giving a freedom to discuss ideas, and promoting enough confidence to tackle problems.
3. Weakness in the field of communications to some extent, may be due to the lack of modernity of communication channels between organization's members and the leadership and the failure of informing the staff about the information related to the tasks assigned to them besides its imprecision and clarity.
4. Clear weakness in the field of expertise and experimentation caused as a result of the lack of following-up the changes and monitoring developments, in addition to the lack of information on competitors in the same industry and a change in the prices of products randomly that do not respond to market requirements, and a clear weakness in expertise and qualifications to obtain that information, which may weaken its competitive and proactive superiority.
5. Exploring the future and searching for new opportunities are at a modest level despite its positivity, which may be due to many reasons, including weakness in internal capabilities, lack of openness to the future, lack of innovation of methods and policies that are compatible with the desires of volatile markets, not to mention the weakness in technological developments and lack of awareness of the importance of available opportunities in the environment.
6. The results of the statistical analysis yielded positive correlations and positive effect relationships with significant indications between the visionary leadership and the exploratory orientation at the level of the main dimensions and at dimensions' level or at sub-variables, except for the relationship and influence between the visionary leadership and future exploration, which gave a justification for rejecting the first sub-hypothesis from the first and second main hypotheses, Whereas, other hypotheses were accepted and validated, including the first and second major hypothesis.

Second: The recommendations:-

1. Emphasizing on the researched company by adopting proactive exploratory positions, seizing the available opportunities in its environment, and innovating policies and methods that are compatible with the volatile market desires.
2. Working on updating the means of communication and its channels between the members and the leadership and informing the principals with all information related to the tasks assigned to them and in a manner that guarantees achieving the vision.
3. Following-up the movements of competing companies and identifying their orientations in order to define strategies and plans proactively and effectively.
4. Creating a state of conformity and harmonization between the internal and external environment of the General Company for Grain Trade through leadership orientations with a clear vision, in addition to conduct continuous environmental analysis and test to keep up with all the fluctuations in the market and in a manner compatible with the requirements of the society's individuals.

REFERENCES

- Al-Dulaimi, Omar Yassin Muhammad Al-Sayer,(2016), "The Intermediate Role of Proactive Orientation in Building Competitive Advantage Based on Marketing Strategies: An Exploratory Study of a Sample of Employees at Asiacell Mobile Communications Company, Iraq, Journal of the College of Economic Sciences, Management and Commercial Sciences.
- Anshar, M, (2017), "The impact of visionary leadership, learning organization and innovative behavior to performance of customs and excise functional. IJHCM" (International Journal of Human Capital Management), 1(02).
- Aragon-Correa, (1998), "Strategic Proactivity and Firm Approach to The Natural Environment", Academic of Management Journal, Vol. 41, No. 5.
- Blocker ,Christopher & Flint ,Daniel, J & Mayer ,Matthew ,B & Sltar ,Stanley ,F, (2011),proactive customer orientation and its role creating customer value in global markets ,academy of marketing science journal , vol (9),PP 216-233.
- Bunnoiko, K., &Atthirawong, W, (2017), "Confirmatory factor analysis towards visionary leadership of supply chain managers in the manufacturing industry of Thailand". Journal for Global Business Advancement, 10(4).
- Cahier du LIPSOR., (2005), "Strategic Foresight, Problems and Approaches, translated by Michel Goody and Qais El Hami, Handbook No. 20, Increased and Revised Edition by Al-Mukhbbar Company and his Partners.
- Christopher P. Blocker & Daniel J. Flint & Matthew B. Myers & Stanley F. Slater,(2011)," Proactive customer orientation and its role for creating customer value in global markets", Academy of Marketing Science.
- Daft, Richard L., (2001), "Organization Theory and Design, south -western college publishing , Ohio", U.S.A
- Dess, G.G. & Lumpkin, G.T., (1996), "Clarifying the Entrepreneurial Orientation Construct and Linking It to Performance", The Academy of Management Review, Vol. 21, No. 1.

The Visionary Leadership's impact on the Strategic role of proactive orientation An analytical research in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade

- Di Benedetto, C. Anthony & Song, Michael, (2003), "The relationship between strategic type and firm capabilities in Chinese firms", *International Marketing Review*, Vol.20 No.5.
- Dwivedi, R. S, (2006), "Visionary leadership: A survey of literature and case study of drapjabdul kalam at drdl. Vision", 10(3).
- Fendi, Ali Hassoun, Saeed, Hadeel Kadhim, Taha, Asma (2013), "The Impact of Applying Impression Management Methods on Roles of Visionary Leadership, An Descriptive Analytical Study at the Ministry of Transport and Communications," *Journal of inclusive Baghdad College for Economic Sciences*, No. (34).
- Frank, Hermann; Kessler, Alexander & Fink, Matthias, (2010), "Entrepreneurial Orientation and Business Performance - A Replication Study", *Schmalenbach Business Review*, Vol.62.
- Hamzah , M. Iskandar & Abdul , K. Othmanb&Faridah , Hassamn , 2015 , Moderating Role of Customer Orientation on the Link between Market Oriented Behaviors and Proactive Service Performance among Relationship Managers in the Business Banking Industry, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 224.
- Johnson , Gerry & Scholes , Kevan & Whittington , Richard , 2008 , exploring corporate strategy , 8 ed. , prentice hall.
- Johnson, G. & Scholes, K., (2002), "Exploring Corporate Strategy", 6 th Edition. Italy, Pearson Education Limited.
- Kearney, E., Shemla, M., van Knippenberg, D., & Scholz, F. A, (2019), "A paradox perspective on the interactive effects of visionary and empowering leadership. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*".
- Kusmiyati, N., & Efendy, H, (2017), "The Visionary of Leadership in Indonesian Navy as a Concept and Effective Strategy towards the World Class Navy". *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 7(4),
- Kwan, D, (2013), "Senior librarians' perceptions on successful leadership skills: A case study" (Doctoral dissertation, University of Phoenix).
- Looy, Bart Van& Martens, Thierry&Bouwen, Rene (2005)" Exploring requisites and antecedents of continuous innovation Working paper, Belgium, pp.(208-221).
- Michael OdeiErdiaw-Kwasie& Michael Yaw Acheampong,(2018)," Empowerment and community salience inmulti-party collaboration: empirical lessons fordevelopmentplanningMichael" , *Development In Practice* , Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group .
- Miles , Ricky w. & Snow , C , 2012 , *Organizational Strategy , Structure and Process* , McGraw-Hill.
- Miles ,R.,&Snow,C, (1978), "Organizational Strategy ,Structure and Process". Mc Graw-Hill, New York,NY.
- Mora-Whitehurst, R, (2013), "The relationship between elementary principals' visionary leadership and students' reading performance. In *The Educational Forum*" (Vol. 77, No. 3, pp. 315-328). Taylor & Francis Group.
- Mupa, P, (2015), "Foundations for Success in the Teaching of O-Level Mathematics in Rural Day Secondary Schools in Masvingo District. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(19).
- Nindyati, A. D,(2013), "Visionary Leadership Measurement in Indonesia*(The Implementation Visionary Leader from Burt Nanus Concept)".

NURUT, M. T. A, (2016), "Undergraduate Thesis (Doctoral Dissertation, Yogyakarta State University)".

The Visionary Leadership's impact on the Strategic role of proactive orientation An analytical research in the Iraqi General Company for Grain Trade

NWACHUKWU, C., CHLADKOVA, H., ZUFAN, P., & OLATUNJI, F, (2017), "Visionary Leadership and Its Relationship with Corporate Social Performance. Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research", 3(4).

NWACHUKWU, C., CHLADKOVA, H., ZUFAN, P., & OLATUNJI, F, (2017), "Visionary Leadership and Its Relationship with Corporate. Social Performance. Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research", 3(4).

Rawolle, M, (2010), "The motivating power of visions: Exploring the Mechanisms".

Westley, & Mintzberg, (1989), "Visionary leadership and Visionary leadership and x Strategic Management Journal", 10, 17-32 .